

Sino-European Innovative Green and Smart Cities

Deliverable 6.2

Project website

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Due date: 31/10/2018
Version: 1.0

Co-funded by the Horizon 2020 programme
of the European Union

Co-funded by the Chinese Ministry
of Science and Technology

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research, and Innovation Programme, under grant Agreement N° 774233

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Co-funded by the Chinese Ministry of Science and Technology

Disclaimer

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SiEUGreen

The project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research, and Innovation programme, under grant Agreement N 774233 and from the Chinese Ministry of Science and Technology.

Throughout SiEUGreen’s implementation, EU and China will share technologies and experiences, thus contributing to the future developments of urban agriculture and urban resilience in both continents.

The project SiEUGreen aspires to enhance the EU-China cooperation in promoting urban agriculture for food security, resource efficiency and smart, resilient cities.

The project contributes to the preparation, deployment and evaluation of showcases in 5 selected European and Chinese urban and peri-urban areas: a previous hospital site in Norway, community gardens in Denmark, previously unused municipal areas with dense refugee population in Turkey, big urban community farms in Beijing and new green urban development in Changsha Central China.

A sustainable business model allowing SiEUGreen to live beyond the project period is planned by joining forces of private investors, governmental policy makers, communities of citizens, academia and technology providers.

SiEUGreen
Sino-European innovative green and smart cities

 facebook.com/SiEUGreen2020

 twitter.com/SiEUGreen

 linkedin.com/groups/8652505

Technical References

Project Acronym:	SiEUGreen
Project Title:	Sino-European Innovative Green and Smart Cities
Project Coordinator:	Dr. Petter D. Jenssen, NMBU Phone: +4791377360 Email: petter.jenssen@nmbu.no
Project Duration:	January 2018 - December 2021

Deliverable N°:	D6.2
Dissemination level ¹:	PU (see explanation bellow)
Work Package:	WP 6 – Communication and dissemination
Task:	Task 6.2 Development of a promotional and knowledge exchange web platform and app
Lead partner:	9 - OKYS
Contributing partner(-s):	6 – EMETRIS
Due date of deliverable:	31/10/2018
Actual submission date:	06/11/2018

¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document History			
Version	Date	Author - Partner	Summary of Changes
1.0	30/09/2018	OKYS	Initial Draft
2.0	06/11/2018	OKYS	Final Version

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Executive Summary

The Deliverable 6.2 “Project Website” provides a “snapshot” of the SiEUGreen project website at the time of writing this document (October 2018) and the project introduction to the public through the factsheet.

Apart from ‘static’ contents (i.e. project description), the project website includes ‘dynamic’ areas where relevant news and announcements for events are regularly (with respect to information on project news and events). All partners will contribute to the content creation and update.

The SiEUGreen website (with web domain “www.sieugreen.eu”), along with the Social Media constitute the primary means of the project’s communication activities, as they are the main communication gate with the project target groups, promoting SiEUGreen activities and events.

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Website goals

The SiEUGreen website is published under the domain www.sieugreen.eu. This website will be used both as communication tool and repository for the project activities, with the aim to:

- **Facilitate communication and knowledge sharing** (events, newsletter, links, downloads for copies of information material)
- **Present the profiles of SiEUGreen network of stakeholders** and facilitate direct engagement through the project Linked Group “SiEUGreen”
- **Present SiEUGreen project** basic information and news
- **Present the showcases** demonstrating their preparation, deployment and evaluation

The website content will be regularly updated, on its content of “news” and “events”, updates to “community”, “cross links with other websites dealing with related research projects” and maintained with improvements to portal design, uploads of documents, and blogs.

The project partners will publish on websites of their organisations, a banner with an abstract of the project and a link to SiEUGreen website.

Currently, a Twitter (<https://twitter.com/SiEUGreen>) has been set to present the SiEUGreen project and help networking. The link is also available “live” at the website.

Finally, the SiEUGreen website will be kept active for a further 5 years upon project completion.

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Website content

The SiEUGreen website has a simple and easy navigate layout. Its content is readable and comprehensive. Additional key features of the website are:

- **Responsive design** (mobile friendly): helps on good ranking on Google search
- **Search Engine Optimizaton**: we have implemented Libraries so keywords will be easy searchable by Google (keywords: urban agriculture, smart cities, green cities, green tech, innovation)
- **High level of security**: we have implemented additional libraries concerning security, like prevention of DDoS, attacks, brute for attacks, encryption of data
- **Twitter feeds**: we developed an advanced Library to show links and images
- **Cookies policy**
- It is written in English, but it is recognizable from online translating tools (e.g. Google translator) to be readable to other languages

Both types content have been included in the portal under certain sections (basic menu). For the management of the content, .NET web framework has been used to support the development.

For each section, there is the possibility to add/edit/delete sub-sections on demand through the administrative interface. The content of the portal will be updated on demand by OKYS and Emetris. Through .NET web framework administration interface the content in all sections can be added/edited/deleted.

The website complies with the current W3C standards, including HTML5, and is optimised for different browsers, including use optimised for different browsers, including use from mobile devices (smartphones and tablets).

The navigation approach of the website is intuitive, thus allowing the visitor to quickly navigate the site starting from any page. It also provides an optimal viewing experience (easy reading and navigation with a minimum of resizing, panning, and scrolling actions).

With regard to the web site design, the current layout delivers a comprehensive structure, yet with a good accessibility. Each page on the website features the project logo.

Moreover, to acknowledge the EU funding, the following sentence is provided together with the EU flag: “This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 774233”.

The following sections present each part of the SiEUGreen website’s content.

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Overall structure

The content of the website has been organized into different pages, as shown below.

Figure 1: Website Menu Bar

Home

The home page is comprised of a top menu bar which contains the different pages with information and links. A state-of-the-art slider has been placed on the top of the page which highlights what the project goals are. Under the slider there are three banners describing the project's objectives.

Beneath there is a section demonstrating the 5 showcases in 5 selected European and Chinese urban and peri-urban areas.

Underneath there are shortcuts that lead to the main project applications. Commurban, the project's resource center and project's stakeholder intranet.

At the bottom there is a list of the latest news (also published to the Social Networks) and there is also a footer noting the copyright and the source project funding.

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SIEUGreen

Developing urban agriculture and urban resilience in Europe and Asia

Developing resilient urban agriculture for food security and urban resilience in Europe and Asia

Project Diary

Objectives

Pilots

The pilot activities have been carried out in a number of pilot sites in Europe and Asia.

Big urban community farms in Beijing, China

SIEUGreen activities in the Beijing pilot sites are focused on urban agriculture for food security and urban resilience. The pilot sites are located in the heart of the city and are used for growing vegetables and fruits. The pilot sites are also used for educational and social activities.

News & Resources

Resource-efficient agricultural techniques

SIEUGreen aims to achieve the EU's objective to promote resource-efficient and sustainable agriculture. This is done by using the best available technologies and practices. SIEUGreen also aims to promote resource-efficient agriculture by using best available technologies and practices. This is done by using the best available technologies and practices.

Statistics

250	SIEUGreen activities in Europe and Asia have resulted in 250 pilot sites in Europe and Asia.	10000	SIEUGreen activities in Europe and Asia have resulted in 10000 pilot sites in Europe and Asia.
250	SIEUGreen activities in Europe and Asia have resulted in 250 pilot sites in Europe and Asia.	10000	SIEUGreen activities in Europe and Asia have resulted in 10000 pilot sites in Europe and Asia.

Resource-efficient agricultural techniques

By using the best available technologies and practices, SIEUGreen aims to achieve the EU's objective to promote resource-efficient and sustainable agriculture. This is done by using the best available technologies and practices.

SIEUGreen explores

SIEUGreen explores the best available technologies and practices for resource-efficient and sustainable agriculture. This is done by using the best available technologies and practices.

SIEUGreen explores

SIEUGreen explores the best available technologies and practices for resource-efficient and sustainable agriculture. This is done by using the best available technologies and practices.

SIEUGreen explores

SIEUGreen explores the best available technologies and practices for resource-efficient and sustainable agriculture. This is done by using the best available technologies and practices.

Figure 2: SiEUGreen Website Home Page

Pilot Interventions

This page is dedicated to the project pilots that will prepare, deploy and evaluate 5 different showcases. There is one page for every different showcase:

- ✓ A previous hospital site in Norway,
- ✓ Community gardens in Denmark,
- ✓ Previously unused municipal areas with dense refugee population in Turkey.
- ✓ Big urban community farms in Beijing, China and
- ✓ A new green urban development in Changsha Central China.

Pilot Areas

SiEUGreen aspires to enhance the EU-China cooperation in promoting urban agriculture for food security, resource efficiency and smart, resilient cities. Building on the model of zero-waste and circular economy, it will demonstrate how technological and societal innovation in urban agriculture can have a positive impact on society and economy, by applying novel resource-efficient agriculture techniques in urban and peri-urban areas, developing innovative approaches for social engagement and empowerment and investigating the economic

Big urban community farms in Beijing China

Aarhus
The overall objective is to strengthen EU-China collaboration in food security and sustainable UA and to develop resilient.

Chansa
The overall objective is to strengthen EU-China collaboration in food security and sustainable UA and to develop resilient.

Fredrikstad
The overall objective is to strengthen EU-China collaboration in food security and sustainable UA and to develop resilient.

Hatay
The overall objective is to strengthen EU-China collaboration in food security and sustainable UA and to develop resilient.

Sanyuan
The overall objective is to strengthen EU-China collaboration in food security and sustainable UA and to develop resilient.

Figure 3: SiEUGreen Website – Showcase Section

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News and Resources

This page includes all the information about the events organised by SiEU Green project and the third-party events that the project is presented.

News & Resources		
Mar, 25	SiEU Green aspires to enhance the EU-China cooperation in promoting urban agriculture for food security, resource efficiency and smart, resilient cities.	>
Mar, 25	SiEU Green aspires to enhance the EU-China cooperation in promoting urban agriculture for food security, resource efficiency and smart, resilient cities.	>
Mar, 25	SiEU Green aspires to enhance the EU-China cooperation in promoting urban agriculture for food security, resource efficiency and smart, resilient cities.	>

Figure 4: SiEU Green Website – New Section

Indicators

The website will provide some of the measurable project performance indicators. The table below show the SiEUGreen project indicators that will be monitored during the project progress.

Indicator	Measurement mean
Number of visits in the project's website	Get statistics of The Pageviews (the total number of pages viewed) using Google analytics.
Number of file downloads	Number of the documents that downloaded from the project website. Counter from the website internal functionality.
Number of publications (articles, press releases, etc.)	Number of views at the dedicated pages of the website for the Press Releases.

Table 1: Indicators

GDBR

As of May 25, 2018, a European privacy law, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), is in effect. The GDPR imposes new rules on companies, government agencies, non-profits, and other organizations that offer goods and services to people in the European Union (EU), or that collect and analyze data tied to EU residents. The GDPR applies no matter where you are located.

The SiEUGreen website is hosted on Microsoft's Azure premises which are physically located in the Netherlands (West Europe Region) and is fully compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

In particular the SiEUGreen website:

- ✓ Protects personal privacy giving individuals the right to:
 - Access their personal data
 - Correct errors in their personal data

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- Erase their personal data
- Object to processing of their personal data
- Export personal data
- ✓ Implements policies like:
 - Notify authorities of personal data breaches
 - Keep records detailing data processing
 - Provide clear notice of data collection
 - Define data retention and deletion policies
 - Audit and update data policies

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